

Investigating the Impact of Science and Technology Education Research on Sustainable Development in Africa

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between science and technology education research and sustainable national development in Nigeria, Africa. The study was guided by three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses. The study adopted correlational research design. The sample size of 256 educational stakeholders in Nigeria was drawn from the population of 26,155 using multi-stage sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was developed by the researchers titled Science and Technology Education Research and Sustainable Development Questionnaire (STERSDQ) was validated by three experts. Reliability coefficient of STERSDQ was established at .84 using Cronbach-Alpha Method. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to answer research questions and also for testing of the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. Findings of the study indicated a higher and significant positive relationship between science and technology education research and sustainable national development in Nigeria, on the indicators such as policy effectiveness, environmental awareness, and social inclusion. Based on the findings the researchers concluded that science and technology education research has higher positive relationship on sustainable national development. In line with the findings of the study researchers recommended amongst other things that African countries should continue to strengthen research policy linkages and institutional capacity building in order to maximize the contribution of science and technology education research for sustainable national development in the African continent.

Introduction

Research in Science and technology education is widely recognized throughout the world as the cornerstone for sustainable national development. Science and technology education research can be described as systematic inquiry into teaching, learning, education policy, curriculum, and related social processes that underpin the overall development of the countries of world, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2020). In Africa, research in science and technology education plays a crucial role in diagnosing key challenges, providing evidence-based solutions for decision making, and guiding reforms that facilitate sustainable national development outcomes of the African nations Nigeria inclusive. Ali (2024) reiterated that science and technology education research is a veritable tool for addressing economic transformation, environmental protection, and social inclusion, Nigeria in particular and Africa in general. According to Tikly, (2019) science and technology education research equips individuals of the country with the desirable knowledge, skills and values necessary to participate effectively in the society to support economic growth, reduce poverty, and promote environmental stewardship that could lead to sustainable of overall national development.

United Nations (2015) posits that sustainable development is the global priority widely referred to as the development that could meet the present societal needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainable development encompasses social equity, economic growth, and environmental protection that centred on United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) vision 2030. It is aimed at ensuring inclusive and equitable quality science and technology education to promote lifelong learning opportunities for all citizens. Sustainable development requires inclusive education that ensures equitable opportunities for all learners, regardless of the gender, socioeconomic status, disability or geographic location.

In Africa, science and technology education research has become increasingly important for sustainable national development as all countries of the world are striving hard to meet the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 4 vision 2030 (United Nations. 2015). This is because science and technology education research has the capacity to contribute immensely to sustainable national development by equipping individuals, educational stakeholders, government, policymakers, educators, communities, and international partners with actionable insights that could help address longstanding inequalities. Creswell and Creswell (2018) maintained that science and technology education research if well implemented have the potential of promoting capacity building, and aligning education with labour market necessary for environmental priorities of the citizens that could meet 2030 vision of UN agenda.

In Africa, achieving UN Sustainable Development Goal 4 vision 2030 is very critical particularly, given the continent rapidly growing population, abundant natural resources, but persistently facing with many challenges such as poverty, inequality, environmental degradation, and limited infrastructure (World Bank, 2018). This means that appropriate research in science and technology education could help to bridge these gaps by providing policymakers, educators and educational stakeholders with adequate knowledge and understanding of the complex relationships between education and sustainable development across all sectors of national economic growth. This means that through evidence-based insights, research informs policies could address the persistent educational challenges such as inequity, poor infrastructure, teacher

shortages, and mismatch between education and labour market needs in our contemporary societies. According to Tikly, (2019) one of the most direct contributions of science and technology education research on sustainable national development is its influence on policy formulation and educational governance as well as environmental sustainability.

The implication is that science and technology education research is capable of providing policymakers with empirical evidence that informs reform agendas, resource allocation, and programme design and evaluation. Zhang, (2024), investigated the relationship between education research on poverty and national sustainability the findings showed a higher positively correlated improvements in the national sustainability indicators across Africa's major economic sectors. This evidence reinforces the argument for government to increased investment and interventions in educational research to support human capacity building development and sustainable outcomes across socioeconomic of every nation.

Science and technology education research is also a strong pillar that supports multistakeholder policy-making frameworks that provides mechanisms for youth-inclusivity. Its facilitates policy review platforms to engage educators, learners, civil society organisations, and decision-makers in collaboration with evidence dialogues to generate contextual relevant opportunities for advancing UN SDG 4 vision 2030 in Nigeria, Africa. These platforms provide spaces for systematic review of the programme implementation progress and the alignment of educational systems with emerging social and labour market needs. Rakgwata and Randima, (2024) carried out a study on inclusive education the results reveal systemic gaps in policy implementation, such as inadequate teacher preparation and resource constraints, which prevent policies from realizing full inclusion outcomes. This study on education inclusivity policies aimed at expanding access to schools for students living with disabilities and the lingering barriers related to resources and social attitudes that continue to be impediment for full participation of students in education systems. Inclusive education research underscores the necessity of indigenous knowledge systems as critical resources for sustainable learning practices that resonate with local cultural contexts, thereby enhancing community ownership and sustainability of educational interventions for the sustainable development of African countries Nigeria inclusive.

The important of science and technology education research cannot be overemphasized. This is because science and technology education research is capable of contributing for economic sustainability of Africa by generating insights on how education systems align better with labour market needs and support innovation and economic growth of the African countries Nigeria inclusive (Zickafoose, 2024). Research into the role of science and technology education in fostering innovation orientation and economic growth have shown that quality education enhances every aspect of country capacity building by stimulating entrepreneurship for sustainable national development. This is central to sustainable national development because it supports individuals' resilience, job creation, and economic diversification in a rapidly changing global economy (World Bank, 2018). Furthermore, studies on the relationship between science and technology and economic growth indicated that science and technology education research has a significantly influence on the employment outcomes, productivity, and social mobility that is the key drivers for the sustainable economic development.

Science and technology education research in the tool that plays a pivotal role in informing skills development strategies, particularly in emerging areas like environmental sustainability and

Information Communication Technology (ICT). Various studies indicate that incorporating digital skills in education could support workforce readiness and enhance opportunities for economic participation that ensure an environmental sustainability.

Environmental sustainability is an integral component of the SDGs that requires science and technology education to equip learners with the knowledge and skills necessary to support environmental stewardship (Abu-Alfoul, 2024). Science and technology education research can help identify effective strategies for integrating sustainable education such as climate change, resource conservation, and ecological ethics into science and technology curricula. By examining learners' behaviours and outcomes, researchers can generate evidence on how education influences environmental attitudes and sustainable practices, thereby informing education policy makers about the practices that aligns with climate goals. Africa generally, Nigeria in particular, where environmental challenges such as desertification, water scarcity, and biodiversity loss are pressing issues, incorporating environmental sustainability into science and technology education will support community resilience and long-term development.

Abdullahi, (2024) opine that enhancement of quality education to achieve UN SDG4 vision 2030 depends on good research in science and technology education. This is because quality research lays groundwork for sustainable livelihoods and socio-economic mobility and growth. Quality education encompasses not only having access to schools, but also the effectiveness of teaching, relevance of the curriculum to the immediate community, and alignment of education with future job markets. Nketsia and Opoku, (2024) observed that quality science and technology education research have potential for strengthen pedagogical skills and curriculum design to prepare better educators to face the contemporary challenges and achieve UN SDG 4 vision 2030 in Sub-Saharan Africa. Science and technology education research helps education stakeholders to identify patterns of inequity and develop evidence-based strategies to promote inclusivity. Research on local knowledge inclusion in education policy highlighted the importance of integrating community-based ways of knowing into national policies to strengthen implementation and promote culturally grounded learning that benefits marginalized groups, including learners with disabilities.

In spite the importance of science and technology education research, Africa countries including Nigeria continued to face significant hurdles in translating educational research into sustainable outcomes. Through the analysis of science and technology education research on specific barriers such as limited access to quality education, teacher shortages, inequitable resource distribution, infrastructure deficits, gender disparities, and rural-urban divides remain persistent across many African countries Nigeria inclusive which still have spotlight to hinder progress toward achieving United Nations SDG 4 vision 2030.

Other challenges hindering utilization of science and technology education research for sustainable development are; continental cultural diversity, linguistic, economic, and environmental needs. This paper investigated the multifaceted ways in which science and technology education research influence sustainable development across Africa Nigeria inclusive, highlighting empirical evidence, policy implications, and transformative pathways. Studies indicate that inadequate funding, teacher shortages, and socio-cultural barriers collectively undermine the delivery of quality education, emphasizing the need for systemic reforms within education sectors (World Bank, 2018). Science and technology education research shows that

science and technology education curriculum integrated sustainability themes such as environmental stewardship, civic participation, and digital literacy in order to produce learners who are better equipped to contribute to socio-economic development of our contemporary society.

Statement of the problem

Despite the potential benefits of science and technology education research on sustainable development many African countries Nigeria inclusive still face constraints of investing in the research. Challenges include limited funding for research activities, gaps in data quality and availability, and insufficient integration of research findings into policy making and practice. To overcome these challenges, increased investment in research infrastructure, capacity-building for researchers, and stronger partnerships between academic institutions, governments and international organizations are needed. Science and technology education research in Africa faces constraints include limited funding for research activities, gaps in data quality and availability, and insufficient integration of research findings into policy making and practices. To overcome these challenges, increased investment in research infrastructure, capacity-building for researchers, and stronger partnerships between academic institutions, governments, and international organizations are needed. Studies exploring quality education and innovation orientation in African contexts show that quality educational outcomes correlate with enhanced innovation capacity in organizations, indicating the broader societal benefits of education research that informs teaching practice and curriculum reforms.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigated the relationship of science and technology education research on sustainable development in Nigeria, Africa. Specifically, the study will seek to:

1. assess the relationship of science and technology education research on environmental sustainability practices across Nigeria.
2. explore relationship of science and technology education research on policy formulation on sustainable development in Nigeria.
3. determine the relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigeria youth.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship of science and technology education research on environmental sustainability practices across Nigeria?
2. What relationship of science on technology education research and policy formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigeria youth?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no relationship of science and technology education research on environmental sustainability practices in Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no relationship of science and technology education research on policy formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigerian youth.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study was 26,155 educational stakeholders in Nigeria. The sample size of 256 was drawn from stakeholders in education by using multi-stage sampling technique was used for the selection of Nigerian educational stakeholders for the study.

The instrument used for data collection was Science and Technology Education Research and Sustainable Development Questionnaire (STERSDQ) which was developed by the researchers. STERSDQ consisted of 30 items, anchored on four-point scale of strongly agree (SA) = 4 points, agree (A) =3 points, disagree (D) =2 points and strongly disagree (SD) =1 point for positively worded items and in the reverse order for the negatively worded items. The validation of the instrument was done by three experts. One in the Department of Integrated Science Education, one Department of Agriculture Education and one from measurement and evaluation the Department of Guidance and Counselling Education both of them are from Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi.

The reliability of STERSDQ was calculated using Cronbach Coefficient Alpha test method which gave the value of 0.84. This value indicated a positive relationship within the test items which showed that items of the instrument are both internally consistent and reliable. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to answer research questions and also for testing of hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Correlation coefficient (r) values from 0.10-0.49 was considered low relationship; r-value from 0.50-0.69 was considered to be moderate relationship, while r-value from 0.70-1.0 was considered high relationship. On the other hand, in testing of hypotheses any hypothesis with a significant value less than p-value of 0.05 was rejected while a hypothesis that had significant value equal to or greater than p-value of 0.05 was withheld.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the relationship of science and technology education research and environmental sustainability practices in Nigeria?

Table 1: Correlation Analysis on relationship of Science and Technology Education Research and Environmental Sustainability

Variables	N	r
Science and Technology Education Research	256	.74
Environmental sustainability		

Results in Table1; shows a Pearson’ coefficient (r) value of .74 which indicates high positive relationship of science and technology education research on environmental sustainability practices in Nigeria. This means that Science and Technology Education Research correlates environmental sustainability with r-value greater than 0.69. This result is further investigated by testing hypothesis one in the Table 2.

Hypothesis 1: There is no relationship between science and technology education research and environmental sustainability practices in Nigeria.

Table 2: Correlation Coefficient of relationship between Science and Technology Education Research and Environmental Sustainability

Variables	N	r	p-value	Significant value	Remark
Science and Technology Education Research	256	.74	.050	.037	Significant
Environmental sustainability					

Table 2; results reveal that the correlational analysis on the relationship between science and technology education research and environmental sustainability have a p-value of .050 and significant value of .037. This significant value of .037 is less than p-value of .050 (i.e. $p=.050>.037$). With this result, the null hypothesis one which stated that there is no relationship between science and technology education research and environmental sustainability practices in Nigeria is rejected. This means that there is a relationship between science and technology education research and environmental sustainability practices in Nigeria.

Research Question 2: what is the relationship of science and technology education research on policy formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria?

Table 3: Correlation Analysis on the relationship of Science and Technology Education Research and Police Formulation for Sustainable Development

Variables	N	r
Science and Technology Education Research	256	.84

policy formulation for sustainable development

Results in Table 3; show a Pearson’ coefficient (r) of .84 which shows a high positive relationship of science and technology education research and policy formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria. This means that STER correlates policy formulation that could lead to sustainable development with r-value above 0.69, this result is further investigated by testing hypothesis two in the Table 4.

Hypothesis 2: There is no relationship of science and technology education research on police formulation for sustainable development in Africa.

Table 4: Correlation Coefficient of the relationship of Science and Technology Education Research on Police Formulation for Sustainable Development

Variables	N	r	p-value	Significant	Remark
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							value	
Science and Technology Research	Education	256	.84	.050	.032		Significant	
policy formulation								

Table 4; results reveal that the correlational analysis on the relationship of science and technology education research on policy formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria have a p-value of .050 and significant value of .032. This significant value of .032 is less than p-value of .050 (i.e. $p=.050>.032$). With this result, the null hypothesis two which stated that there is no relationship of science and technology education research on police formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria is rejected. This means that there is a relationship of science and technology education research on policy formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigeria youth?

Table 5: Correlation Analysis on relationship of Science and Technology Education Research on Innovation and Technological Capacity Building

Variables	N	R
Science and Technology Education Research	256	.72

Innovation and capacity building among the youth

Results in Table5; reveals a Pearson' coefficient (r) of .72 which shows a high positive relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among the youth in Nigeria. This means that STER have a highly correlates Innovation and technological capacity building among the youth with r-value above 0.69, this finding is further investigated by testing hypothesis three in the Table 6.

Hypothesis 3: There is no relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigerian youth

Table 6: Correlation Coefficient of Science and Technology Education Research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigerian youth.

Variables	N	R	p-value	Significant value	Remark
Science and Technology Research	256	.72	.050	.032	significant

policy formulation

Table 6; results reveal that the correlational analysis on the relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigerian youth have a p-value of .050 and significant value of .042, this significant value is less than p-value of .050 (i.e. $p=.050>.042$). With this result, the null hypothesis three which stated that There is no relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigerian youth is rejected. This means that there is a relationship of

science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigerian youth.

Summary of Major Findings

1. There is a relationship of science and technology education research on environmental sustainability practices in Nigeria.
2. There is a relationship of science and technology education research on policy formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria.
3. There is a relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigerian youth

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study revealed a positive higher relationship of science and technology education research on environmental sustainability practices in Nigeria. This finding is in consonance with that of Nketsia and Opoku (2024) who revealed that science and technology education research has a higher positive relationship on environmental sustainability in African country Nigeria.

Results of this study also revealed a higher and positive relationship of science and technology education research on policy formulation for sustainable development in Nigeria. This finding is in line with Tikly, (2019) and Zhang (2024) who in their various studies found out that science and technology education research correlates policy formulation for sustainable national development of the African countries.

Findings of this study showed a higher positive relationship of science and technology education research on innovation and technological capacity building among Nigerian youth. This finding is in agreement with that of Abdullahi, (2024) and Ali, (2024) who revealed that science and technology education research has a positive relationship on innovation and technological capacity building among African youth Nigeria inclusive.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study the researchers concluded that science and technology education research has higher positive relationship on sustainable development in Nigeria, Africa. This higher positive relationship is prominent in the area of environmental sustainability, policy formulation that enable sustainable national development as well as innovation and technological capacity building among African youth including Nigeria.

Recommendation

In line with the findings of the study researchers recommended that:

1. African countries should continue to strengthen research policy linkages and institutional capacity building in order to maximize the contribution of science and technology education research for sustainable national development in the Nigeria

country.

2. Governments and development partners should establish mechanisms to ensure science and technology education research informs policy formulation and implementation, particularly for achieving United Nations SDG 4 vision 2030. Stakeholders in Nigeria and Africa as whole also should explore effective strategies for enhancing the integration of science and technology education research into effective national sustainable development plans.
3. Government at all levels should invest in institutional capacity building programmes by enhancing governance structures that ensure research findings are operationalized to maximize education's contribution to sustainable development.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, A. M. (2024). *The impact of education for sustainable development on university students' sustainability behaviour: a case study from Somalia*. *Frontiers in Education*.
- Abu Alfoul, M. N. (2024). *The effect of education on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries: do institutions matter?* MDPI.
- Ali, U. F. (2024). Integrating Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the Ugandan Education System. *Research Inventions Journals* 4(2) 12-25.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (5th ed.). Sage Publications
- Nketsia, W., & Opoku, M. P. (2024). *Frontiers in Transforming Teacher Education*. *Frontiers in Education*.
- Tikly, L. (2019). Education for sustainable development in Africa: A critique of regional agendas. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 20(2), 223–237.
- UNESCO. (2020). *Global education monitoring report*. Paris: UNESCO.
- United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development*.
- World Bank. (2018). *World development report: Learning to realize education's promise*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- Zhang, X. (2024). *Sustainable development in African countries: evidence from the impacts of education and poverty ratio*. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*.
- Zickafoose, A. et al. (2024). *Barriers and challenges affecting quality education in sub-Saharan Africa*. *Sustainability*.